

More transparency on glyphosate: BfR supports the release by EFSA of raw scientific data

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The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) announced on 29 September 2016 that it would release the raw data of the studies used in the renewal procedure for the active substance glyphosate on a European level. Scientists can now comprehensively review and evaluate the European assessment along with the extensive reference documentation that has already been published on the EFSA website.

By releasing the raw data of the applicants' studies, EFSA will create even more transparency with regard to the assessment of glyphosate while continuing to fulfil the obligations imposed by European law regarding the protection of sensitive economic information and trade and corporate secrets.

The Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) expressly welcomes this intention.

Glyphosate is one of 485 active substances in plant protection products currently approved in the EU and – just like every other pesticidal active substance – it is reassessed at regular intervals within the scope of EU active substance testing with regard to the risks it poses to health and the environment, as well as its efficacy, by the member states and European Food Safety Authority (EFSA).

The rapporteur member state for the joint testing and assessment of glyphosate was Germany. Within the renewal procedure, the Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) was commissioned with the assessment of the health risk posed by the active substance. The BfR's assessment of the health risks of glyphosate shows that according to current scientific knowledge, no carcinogenic risk is to be expected if the substance is used correctly and in line with its intended purpose. This assessment was confirmed by the experts of the member states and EFSA, as well as those of the WHO/FAO committee *Joint FAO/WHO Meeting on Pesticide Residues* (JMPR). EFSA presented its final evaluation (EFSA Conclusion) to the European Commission and member states of the European Union on the basis of the joint assessment. The Renewal Assessment Report, including the related supplements added after the evaluation of the public and specialised consultations (Peer Review Report) and the BfR addendum on the assessment of the IARC monograph, has been published on the EFSA website under www.efsa.europa.eu.

These documents can be viewed at:

<http://registerofquestions.efsa.europa.eu/roqFrontend/ListOfQuestionsNoLogin>

The JMPR assessment was also published in full and can be accessed at:

<http://apps.who.int/pesticide-residues-jmpr-database/pesticide?name=GLYPHOSATE>

Despite this high level of transparency, repeated requests were made to review the original studies in order to verify and validate the scientific assessment made by the authorities. Publication of the raw data will now enable the professional public in particular to better comprehend the estimation of the BfR and EFSA, as well as the details of the assessment process, and clarify any misunderstandings in an open discussion process.

This step towards disclosing the raw data can also serve as an incentive to open up other ways of using official data for further-reaching scientific analysis and introduce this wealth of knowledge to the scientific community as a data basis while still complying with the obligations imposed by European law regarding the protection of sensitive economic information and trade and corporate secrets.

More BfR information on the subject of glyphosate

BfR publications on the subject of glyphosate:

http://www.bfr.bund.de/en/a-z_index/glyphosate-193962.html

<http://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/343/eu-genehmigungsverfahren-von-pflanzenschutzmittelwirkstoffen-infografik.pdf>

About the BfR

The Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) is a scientifically independent institution within the portfolio of the Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture (BMEL) in Germany. It advises the Federal Government and Federal Laender on questions of food, chemical and product safety. The BfR conducts its own research on topics that are closely linked to its assessment tasks.

Link to

EFSA press release of 29 September 2016:

<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/press/news/160929a>

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